

EULER-LAGRANGE MODELING OF GAS-SOLID FLOW IN A CIRCULATING FLUIDIZED BED RISER: EVALUATION AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Daiane Francisca do Nascimento Silva¹

Jean Firmino Cardoso²

Fabian Luis Mena de la Noval³

Abel Gámez Rodríguez⁴

Yaicel Ge Proenza⁵

Antonio Celso Dantas Antonino⁶

José Miguel Reichert⁷

Daniel Milian Pérez⁸

ABSTRACT

Introduction: This study presents the development and evaluation of a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model utilizing the Euler-Lagrange approach to simulate gas-solid flow within a circulating fluidized bed (CFB) riser. The research aims to enhance the understanding of multiphase dynamics in such systems, addressing limitations of prior Euler-Euler models. Using ANSYS CFX, two types of simulations were performed: initial steady-state simulations were conducted to calibrate and evaluate the models' behavior, followed by transient simulations to investigate the system's time-dependent dynamics. All simulations were isothermal, modeling air as the continuous phase and Nylon-66 particles as the dispersed phase. Key findings indicate that flow movement is concentrated at the riser's inlet, forming a high-intensity jet, with particle velocities aligning with expected values (0.5-2.0 m/s). Pressure distributions exhibited typical patterns for upward two-phase flows, showing significant drops at the inclined solid inlet and stable conditions in the vertical section. While this modeling approach accurately captured turbulent effects in critical inlet regions, the study acknowledges limitations, including computational time constraints and the exclusion of heat transfer effects. This work significantly contributes to the literature by providing a detailed understanding of two-phase flow in risers and offering a robust, compared Euler-Lagrange computational model that surmounts the inherent practical and informational limitations of purely experimental investigations, laying a solid foundation for future research and optimization in industrial applications like Fluid Catalytic Cracking (FCC) processes.

Objective: This study develops and evaluates an Euler-Lagrange CFD model to simulate gas-solid flow in circulating fluidized bed (CFB) risers. It aims to enhance the understanding of multiphase flow dynamics, address the limitations of Euler-Euler models, and compare the model's performance against existing numerical data from the literature.

Theoretical Framework: The theoretical framework outlines key concepts of multiphase flow, emphasizing the use of cold riser pilot units to simulate industrial reactor behavior. It also presents the fundamentals of

¹ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: daiane.francisca@ufpe.br

Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1057-7335>

² Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: jean.firmino@ufpe.br

Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6092-713X>

³ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: fabian.mena@ufpe.br

Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0335-542>

⁴ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: abel.rodriiguez@ufpe.br

Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1584-6768>

⁵ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: yaicel.geproenza@ufpe.br

Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3894-8326>

⁶ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: antonio.antonino@ufpe.br

Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4120-9404>

⁷ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: reichert@ufsm.br

Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9943-2898>

⁸ Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil. E-mail: daniel.milian@ufpe.br

Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3172-0508>

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), detailing its methodology, relevant modeling approaches, and its complementary role alongside experimental studies in addressing traditional limitations.

Method: This computational study employed ANSYS CFX to perform steady-state, isothermal simulations of gas-solid flow in a vertical riser, modeling air as the continuous phase and Nylon-66 particles as the dispersed phase. The SST turbulence model and coupled interphase interactions were implemented to characterize flow behavior and collect key variables.

Results and Discussion: The results showed that flow was concentrated near the riser inlet, forming a high-intensity jet. Particle velocities were within expected ranges, and pressure profiles exhibited typical patterns for upward two-phase flow, including significant drops at the solid inlet and stable values along the riser. The discussion also addressed modeling limitations, such as the absence of thermal effects and computational time constraints.

Research Implications: This research contributes to the advancement of multiphase flow modeling in chemical engineering by improving the understanding of gas-solid dynamics in risers. Its implications include supporting industrial process design, complementing experimental studies, and offering a foundation for future numerical and hybrid modeling efforts.

Originality/Value: The study's originality lies in developing and evaluating an Euler-Lagrange CFD model that addresses the limitations of Euler-Euler formulations in capturing particle-scale phenomena. It provides an in-depth computational analysis that advances the understanding of multiphase flow behavior in risers.

Keywords: CFD, Euler-Lagrange, Riser, Multiphase flow, Fluidized bed, and Computational modeling.

MODELAGEM EULER-LAGRANGE DO ESCOAMENTO GÁS-SÓLIDO EM UM RISER DE LEITO FLUIDIZADO CIRCULANTE: AVALIAÇÃO E ANÁLISE COMPARATIVA

RESUMO

Introdução: Este estudo apresenta o desenvolvimento e a avaliação de um modelo de Dinâmica dos Fluidos Computacional (CFD) baseado na abordagem Euler-Lagrange para simular o escoamento gás-sólido em um riser de leito fluidizado circulante (CFB). A pesquisa tem como objetivo ampliar a compreensão da dinâmica multifásica nesse tipo de sistema, abordando limitações associadas a modelos anteriores baseados na formulação Euler-Euler. Utilizando o ANSYS CFX, dois tipos de simulações foram realizadas: simulações iniciais em regime permanente, utilizadas para calibrar e avaliar o comportamento do modelo, seguidas por simulações transientes para investigar a dinâmica temporal do sistema. Todas as simulações foram isotérmicas, modelando o ar como fase contínua e as partículas de Nylon-66 como fase dispersa. Os principais resultados indicam que o escoamento se concentra na entrada do riser, formando um jato de alta intensidade, com velocidades de partículas compatíveis com os valores esperados (0,5–2,0 m/s). As distribuições de pressão apresentaram padrões típicos de escoamentos bifásicos ascendentes, com quedas acentuadas na entrada inclinada de sólidos e condições estáveis ao longo da seção vertical. Embora essa abordagem de modelagem tenha capturado com precisão características importantes do escoamento nas regiões críticas de entrada, o estudo reconhece limitações, como restrições de tempo computacional e a exclusão de efeitos de transferência de calor. Este trabalho contribui significativamente para a literatura ao fornecer uma compreensão detalhada do escoamento bifásico em risers e ao oferecer um modelo computacional robusto baseado na abordagem Euler-Lagrange, que supera limitações práticas e informacionais inerentes aos estudos puramente experimentais, estabelecendo uma base sólida para pesquisas futuras e otimizações em aplicações industriais, como nos processos de craqueamento catalítico fluido (FCC).

Objetivo: Este estudo desenvolve e avalia um modelo CFD baseado na abordagem Euler-Lagrange para simular o escoamento gás-sólido em risers de leito fluidizado circulante (CFB). O objetivo é aprimorar a compreensão da dinâmica de escoamentos multifásicos, superar as limitações dos modelos Euler-Euler e comparar o desempenho do modelo com dados numéricos existentes na literatura.

Referencial Teórico: O referencial teórico apresenta os principais conceitos sobre escoamento multifásico, com ênfase no uso de unidades piloto de riser a frio para simular o comportamento de reatores industriais. Também são abordados os fundamentos da Dinâmica dos Fluidos Computacional (CFD), detalhando sua metodologia, os modelos relevantes e seu papel complementar aos estudos experimentais na superação de limitações tradicionais.

Método: Este estudo computacional utilizou o ANSYS CFX para realizar simulações em regime permanente e isotérmico do escoamento gás-sólido em um riser vertical, modelando o ar como fase contínua e partículas de Nylon-66 como fase dispersa. O modelo de turbulência SST e as interações entre fases foram implementados para caracterizar o comportamento do escoamento e coletar as variáveis de interesse.

Resultados e Discussão: Os resultados indicaram que o escoamento se concentrou na região próxima à entrada do riser, formando um jato de alta intensidade. As velocidades das partículas permaneceram dentro dos intervalos esperados, e os perfis de pressão apresentaram padrões típicos de escoamentos bifásicos ascendentes, com quedas significativas na entrada inclinada de sólidos e comportamento estável ao longo da seção vertical. A discussão também abordou limitações do modelo, como a ausência de efeitos térmicos e as restrições de tempo computacional.

Implicações da Pesquisa: Esta pesquisa contribui para o avanço da modelagem de escoamentos multifásicos na engenharia química, aprimorando a compreensão da dinâmica gás-sólido em risers. Suas implicações incluem o suporte ao projeto de processos industriais, a complementação de estudos experimentais e o fornecimento de uma base para futuros trabalhos numéricos e híbridos.

Originalidade/Valor: A originalidade do estudo reside no desenvolvimento e avaliação de um modelo CFD baseado na abordagem Euler-Lagrange, que supera limitações das formulações Euler-Euler na representação de fenômenos em escala de partículas. O trabalho oferece uma análise computacional aprofundada que contribui para o avanço da compreensão do comportamento multifásico em risers.

Palavras-chave: CFD, Euler-Lagrange, Riser, Fluxo Multifásico, Leito Fluidizado, Modelagem Computacional.

MODELADO EULER-LAGRANGE DEL FLUJO GAS-SÓLIDO EN UN RISER DE LECHO FLUIDIZADO CIRCULANTE: EVALUACIÓN Y ANÁLISIS COMPARATIVO

RESUMEN

Introducción: Este estudio presenta el desarrollo y la evaluación de un modelo de Dinámica de Fluidos Computacional (CFD) basado en el enfoque Euler-Lagrange para simular el flujo gas-sólido en un riser de lecho fluidizado circulante (CFB). La investigación tiene como objetivo mejorar la comprensión de la dinámica multifásica en este tipo de sistemas, abordando las limitaciones de modelos anteriores basados en la formulación Euler-Euler. Utilizando ANSYS CFX, se realizaron dos tipos de simulaciones: simulaciones iniciales en estado estacionario, utilizadas para calibrar y evaluar el comportamiento del modelo, seguidas de simulaciones transitorias para investigar la dinámica temporal del sistema. Todas las simulaciones fueron isotérmicas, modelando el aire como fase continua y partículas de Nylon-66 como fase dispersa. Los principales resultados indican que el flujo se concentra en la entrada del riser, formando un chorro de alta intensidad, con velocidades de partículas dentro de los rangos esperados (0,5–2,0 m/s). Las distribuciones de presión mostraron patrones típicos de flujos bifásicos ascendentes, con caídas significativas en la entrada inclinada de sólidos y condiciones estables a lo largo de la sección vertical. Aunque este enfoque de modelado capturó con precisión características importantes del flujo en regiones críticas de entrada, el estudio reconoce ciertas limitaciones, como las restricciones de tiempo computacional y la exclusión de efectos de transferencia de calor. Este trabajo contribuye significativamente a la literatura al proporcionar una comprensión detallada del flujo bifásico en risers y al ofrecer un modelo computacional robusto basado en el enfoque Euler-Lagrange, que supera las limitaciones prácticas e informativas inherentes a los estudios puramente experimentales, estableciendo una base sólida para futuras investigaciones y optimizaciones en aplicaciones industriales como los procesos de craqueo catalítico fluido (FCC).

Objetivo: Este estudio desarrolla y evalúa un modelo CFD basado en el enfoque Euler-Lagrange para simular el flujo gas-sólido en risers de lecho fluidizado circulante (CFB). El objetivo es mejorar la comprensión de la dinámica de flujos multifásicos, superar las limitaciones de los modelos Euler-Euler y comparar el desempeño del modelo con datos numéricos existentes en la literatura.

Marco Teórico: El marco teórico presenta los conceptos clave del flujo multifásico, con énfasis en el uso de unidades piloto de riser en frío para simular el comportamiento de reactores industriales. También se abordan los fundamentos de la Dinámica de Fluidos Computacional (CFD), detallando su metodología, los enfoques de modelado relevantes y su papel complementario a los estudios experimentales en la superación de limitaciones tradicionales.

Método: Este estudio computacional utilizó ANSYS CFX para realizar simulaciones isotérmicas en estado estacionario del flujo gas-sólido en un riser vertical, modelando el aire como fase continua y partículas de Nylon-66 como fase dispersa. Se implementaron el modelo de turbulencia SST y las interacciones entre fases para caracterizar el comportamiento del flujo y recolectar las variables clave.

Resultados y Discusión: Los resultados mostraron que el flujo se concentró cerca de la entrada del riser, formando un chorro de alta intensidad. Las velocidades de las partículas se mantuvieron dentro de los rangos esperados y los perfiles de presión presentaron patrones típicos de flujo bifásico ascendente, con caídas significativas en la entrada inclinada de sólidos y comportamiento estable a lo largo de la sección vertical. La discusión también abordó las limitaciones del modelo, como la ausencia de efectos térmicos y las restricciones de tiempo computacional.

Implicaciones de la Investigación: Esta investigación contribuye al avance del modelado de flujos multifásicos en la ingeniería química, mejorando la comprensión de la dinámica gas-sólido en risers. Sus implicaciones incluyen el apoyo al diseño de procesos industriales, la complementación de estudios experimentales y la provisión de una base para futuros estudios numéricos e híbridos.

Originalidad/Valor: La originalidad del estudio radica en el desarrollo y evaluación de un modelo CFD basado en el enfoque Euler-Lagrange, que supera las limitaciones de las formulaciones Euler-Euler en la representación de fenómenos a escala de partícula. El trabajo ofrece un análisis computacional detallado que contribuye al avance de la comprensión del comportamiento multifásico en risers.

Palabras clave: CFD, Euler-Lagrange, Riser, Flujo Multifásico, Lecho Fluidizado, Modelado Computacional.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The investigation and optimization of multiphase flow reactors, particularly riser reactors and fluidized bed reactors, constitute a central focus in key industrial processes such as Fluid Catalytic Cracking (FCC) and the conversion of crude oil into high-value chemicals (Chang *et al.*, 2012; Chen *et al.*, 2021; Cui *et al.*, 2024; Du *et al.*, 2022; Shah *et al.*, 2025; Tripoonsuk *et al.*, 2025; Wang *et al.*, 2024). Riser reactors are critical components in the petrochemical industry, with the FCC process being fundamental for converting heavy, high-boiling point, and high-molecular-weight hydrocarbons into more valuable products like gasoline, olefinic gases, and other derivatives (Chang *et al.*, 2012; Chen *et al.*, 2021; Du *et al.*, 2022; Wang *et al.*, 2024).

Globally, FCC accounts for approximately 45% of gasoline and one-third of propylene production, and it stands as the most vital and profitable process for heavy oil conversion (Chang *et al.*, 2012). Advanced technologies, such as TMP (two-stage riser catalytic cracking for propylene maximization) and RTC (Residue to Chemicals), employ innovative riser reactor designs to optimize light olefin production and accommodate heavier feedstocks (Du *et al.*, 2022; Wang *et al.*, 2024). Continuous advancements in FCC technology aim to enhance the

processing of heavier feeds, comply with stringent environmental regulations, and increase product yields (Chang *et al.*, 2012).

The operation of these reactors is inherently complex due to the multiphase nature of the flow, which involves the turbulent interaction of gas, feedstock droplets, and catalyst particles (Chang *et al.*, 2012; Chen *et al.*, 2021). The feedstock injection zone, in particular, is a critical area where gas-solid-liquid mixing, vaporization, and cracking reactions occur simultaneously (Chen *et al.*, 2021). Heterogeneous flow distributions within riser reactors directly impact both axial and radial flow structures, consequently influencing the final product quality (Gómez-Velásquez *et al.*, 2021). Common issues include the formation of particle "clusters" near the reactor walls, which reduce the catalyst contact area and, consequently, reaction performance (Gómez-Velásquez *et al.*, 2021). With the processing of increasingly heavier crude oil feedstocks, coke formation becomes a more severe concern, leading to rapid catalyst deactivation, reduced desired product yields, and increased energy consumption (Chen *et al.*, 2021).

Given the complexity of these phenomena (momentum/heat transfer and cracking reactions) and the severe operating conditions (high temperatures and pressures), detailed experimental investigation in industrial reactors is often impractical and challenging (Chang *et al.*, 2012; Du *et al.*, 2022). In response to this limitation, numerical simulation and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) have emerged as indispensable tools for exploring and predicting these complex processes in the petrochemical industry (Chang *et al.*, 2012; Chen *et al.*, 2021; Du *et al.*, 2022; Tripoonsuk *et al.*, 2025; Wang *et al.*, 2024). Models such as the Eulerian-Eulerian method are frequently employed to simulate multiphase flows in medium- and large-scale domains characteristic of industrial processes, owing to their ability to utilize relatively coarse numerical grids, often being the only feasible approach (Crowe *et al.*, 1996; Gómez-Velásquez *et al.*, 2021; Tripoonsuk *et al.*, 2025).

However, these methods have limitations in capturing detailed particle-scale information, such as trajectories and residence time (Du *et al.*, 2022). To overcome these limitations, particle-scale models like MP-PIC (Multiphase Particle-in-Cell) and CPFDP (Computational Particle Fluid Dynamics), which utilize a Lagrangian description for the solid phase, are developed to provide highly detailed information on particle movements (Du *et al.*, 2022; Villafañe *et al.*, 2025). Additionally, the incorporation of kinetic cracking models, such as 8- or 12-lump models, is crucial for describing the reaction process and predicting product yields (Chang *et al.*, 2012; Chen *et al.*, 2021; Du *et al.*, 2022; Wang *et al.*, 2024). Drag models based on the EMMS (Energy-Minimization Multi-Scale) principle are also employed to address

the heterogeneity of flow structures (Chen *et al.*, 2021; Du *et al.*, 2022; Wang *et al.*, 2024).

Despite significant advancements in numerical simulation, experimental validation remains of paramount importance. Computational models are validated by comparing them with industrial or bench-scale experimental data to ensure their accuracy and reliability in predicting reactor performance (Chang *et al.*, 2012; Crowe *et al.*, 1996; Du *et al.*, 2022; Gómez-Velásquez *et al.*, 2021; Riaz *et al.*, 2025; Tripoonsuk *et al.*, 2025; Villafañe *et al.*, 2025; Wang *et al.*, 2024). It is crucial to acknowledge that no single experimental technique or numerical simulation can simultaneously capture all three-dimensional properties of dispersed and continuous phases in a time-resolved manner (Villafañe *et al.*, 2025). Validation allows for the identification and correction of missing physics or inaccuracies in theoretical models, being fundamental for the advancement of multiphase flow science and technology (Villafañe *et al.*, 2025).

This work proposes the development and evaluation of a computational model based on the Euler-Lagrange approach to simulate gas-solid flow in a circulating fluidized bed (CFB) riser. The objective is to deepen the understanding of multiphase dynamics in such systems, addressing the limitations of traditional Euler-Euler models. To achieve this, the study focuses on implementing an Euler-Lagrange CFD model to simulate the gas-solid interactions occurring within the riser of the experimental unit at the Dr. Cornelius Keller Gamma Tomography Laboratory, located in the Department of Nuclear Energy at the Federal University of Pernambuco. The simulations will consider well-established physical properties and flow conditions relevant to the system under investigation.

To achieve this overarching goal, several specific objectives will be addressed. First, the study will seek to evaluate the axial and radial distribution of solid volume fraction within the riser, comparing the results obtained with those from previous studies that employed other approaches. Subsequently, it will be crucial to analyze the influence of gas velocity and solid flux on the flow behavior, verifying the formation of high particle concentration regions near the walls and the homogeneity of the flow in the riser's center.

An evaluation of the proposed model constitutes an essential step of this study. Rather than experimental validation, the performance of the Euler-Lagrange model is assessed through comparisons with data and results from previous experimental and numerical studies available in the literature. These comparisons aim to verify the consistency of the flow behavior, including solid volume fraction, pressure drop, and particle velocity distributions. Additionally, the study explores the advantages and limitations of the Euler-Lagrange approach relative to the Euler-Euler method, highlighting key aspects such as its ability to resolve individual particle

trajectories, the trade-offs between computational cost and accuracy, and the capacity to capture local phenomena like particle agglomeration and segregation. This analysis provides a foundation for advancing numerical modeling strategies in gas-solid riser systems.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Cold riser pilot units are experimental, often scaled-down, models that simulate the fluid dynamic behavior of larger industrial hot reactors, such as those found in dual fluidized bed (DFB) systems or FCC units (Habl *et al.*, 2017; Hanchate *et al.*, 2021; Shrestha *et al.*, 2016). To achieve this, they operate under ambient conditions, utilizing air and non-reacting solids (e.g., bronze powder or quartz sand), instead of elevated temperatures and reactive agents (Habl *et al.*, 2017; Hanchate *et al.*, 2021; Shrestha *et al.*, 2016). These units are designed based on scaling relationships, such as Glicksman's criteria, to ensure hydrodynamic similarity between the model and the actual plant (Habl *et al.*, 2017; Shrestha *et al.*, 2016).

These units are extensively employed in the petroleum industry and related processes for several important reasons, including the complexity of flow and measurement difficulties under real conditions, risk reduction and process optimization, and the analysis of specific phenomena and validation of computational models.

The complexity of flow and measurement difficulties under real conditions are crucial factors. Riser reactors, such as those in FCC units, are complex multiphase systems (gas, solids, and sometimes liquid droplets), and their design and scaling are largely empirical due to a limited understanding of the inherent flow (Shah *et al.*, 2016). Similarly, DFB systems, which frequently include risers, operate with complexity due to interactions among components such as the gasifier, riser, cyclone, and loop seal (Hanchate *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, it is challenging to measure fundamental hydrodynamic parameters (such as pressure drop, solids fraction, and solids circulation rate) in industrial plants under hot, reactive operating conditions, as these measurements can be superficial and not representative of actual conditions (Shrestha *et al.*, 2016).

The use of cold models contributes to risk reduction and process optimization. They help minimize the risks associated with scaling complex units to commercial sizes, allowing for the maintenance of "microstructure similarity" (internal flow dynamics) between the model and the larger unit (Breault, 2024). These models provide crucial engineering data for the design and scaling of commercial units (Hanchate *et al.*, 2021; Shrestha *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, they allow for the investigation of the effect of various operational parameters on the system's

hydrodynamics and performance, such as solids circulation rate, mixing efficiency, pressure profiles, and solids holdup (Habl *et al.*, 2017; Hanchate *et al.*, 2021; Shah *et al.*, 2017; Shrestha *et al.*, 2016). For FCC risers, for instance, improving gas-solid mixing is essential for achieving higher performance (Shah *et al.*, 2017).

Finally, these units are fundamental for the analysis of specific phenomena and validation of computational models. In FCC units, they are used to investigate heterogeneous flow patterns, such as "core-annular" flow and "S-shaped" axial profiles, as well as the formation of particle "clusters," all of which affect mixing (Shah *et al.*, 2016, 2017). They are also employed to study the impact of different design solutions and operational strategies, such as the effect of pulsating flow on hydrodynamics and gas-solid mixing (Shah *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, they are crucial for understanding and optimizing the solids circulation rate (SCR) in DFB systems, a vital parameter for heat transfer and fuel efficiency in gasification and combustion processes (Hanchate *et al.*, 2021; Shrestha *et al.*, 2016).

The results obtained from cold models can be translated to pilot plant conditions, aiding in the development and validation of CFD models to predict reactive flow in FCC risers, especially where experimental data under hot conditions are scarce (Habl *et al.*, 2017; Shah *et al.*, 2016, 2017). From a practical standpoint, cold models are more economical, require less experimental equipment and control techniques, and allow for direct visual observation of macroscopic flow structures, making them a reliable source of fluid dynamic data (Shrestha *et al.*, 2016). CFD simulation is a powerful tool for investigating complex flow phenomena (Zhang *et al.*, 2025). It enables the simulation of heterogeneous systems, such as those involving liquids, gases, and solids, and provides detailed information on important physical fields (Zhang *et al.*, 2025).

Fundamentally, CFD involves solving the partial differential equations of fluid mechanics, such as the Navier-Stokes equations, in space and time, using numerical methods (Zhang *et al.*, 2025). A typical CFD simulation process is divided into three main stages: pre-processing, solving, and post-processing (Zhang *et al.*, 2025). The pre-processing stage deals with complex geometries and dynamic problems, involving the generation of computational meshes that discretize the flow domain. The challenge lies in creating high-resolution meshes without incurring prohibitive computational costs or introducing numerical instabilities (Zhang *et al.*, 2025). The core of CFD is the solving stage, which involves the continuous updating of control volume values until convergence criteria are met (Zhang *et al.*, 2025). For this, different approaches and models are utilized. Multiphase models in CFD can employ various frameworks, such as Euler-Euler (E-E), where both the gas and solid phases are treated as

interpenetrating continua (Shah *et al.*, 2016, 2017; Sun *et al.*, 2023), or Euler-Lagrange (E-L), which combines the Eulerian framework for fluids with the Lagrangian framework for discrete particles (as in CFD-DEM), the latter being suitable for low to medium concentrations (Zhang *et al.*, 2025). For free surface flows, such as in boiling processes or bed flows, the Volume of Fluid (VOF) method is widely used (Nian *et al.*, 2021; Nigim, 2023). Furthermore, governing equations and closure models are crucial. Conservation equations for mass, momentum, and energy are solved for each phase (Reiss *et al.*, 2024; Shah *et al.*, 2016, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2025). To describe complex interactions and phenomena, closure models are necessary, including drag models for fluid-particle interaction (Nian *et al.*, 2021; Shah *et al.*, 2016, 2017; Sun *et al.*, 2023), models for solid phase stresses (such as the Kinetic Theory of Granular Flow - KTGF), and turbulence models (such as k-epsilon, k-omega, or Reynolds stress models - RSM, and Large Eddy Simulation - LES) to capture turbulent flow behavior (Shah *et al.*, 2016, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2025). Finally, defining boundary conditions (such as inlet, outlet, and walls) is crucial and can significantly influence the accuracy and stability of the results (Shah *et al.*, 2016, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2025). In the post-processing stage, after solving, the simulation results are analyzed and visualized to provide insights into flow behavior (Zhang *et al.*, 2025). At this stage, it is also common to assess the consistency of the results by comparing them with experimental data, analytical models, or findings from the literature. Such comparisons help verify whether the predicted flow patterns and key variables align with expected physical behavior, thereby enhancing confidence in the numerical approach (Mirzaei *et al.*, 2023; Porcu *et al.*, 2023; Reiss *et al.*, 2024; Shah *et al.*, 2017; Sun *et al.*, 2023).

Cold flow modeling, especially for complex geometries like DFB systems, is widely used in the scientific community to understand reactor fluid dynamics (Habl *et al.*, 2017; Hanchate *et al.*, 2021; Shrestha *et al.*, 2016). CFD complements and enhances these studies in several ways. CFD assists in understanding internal fluid dynamics. Cold flow studies are conducted to comprehend the fluid dynamics within gasifiers, being useful for simulating operationally complex systems (Hanchate *et al.*, 2021). CFD, in turn, allows for the analysis of phase distribution, pressure, and velocity in microscopic detail, providing guidance for design and control parameters (Tang *et al.*, 2024). It can predict holdup profiles, velocity profiles, and solid distribution (Shah *et al.*, 2017), offering an in-depth view of hydrodynamic characteristics, such as core-annular flow patterns and solid segregation (Shah *et al.*, 2017). CFD is fundamental for design optimization and verification. It is essential for verifying and optimizing design criteria, enabling qualitative and quantitative measurements of mixing, separation, pressure drop, and erosion (Hanchate *et al.*, 2021). Cold flow models are designed and built

according to similarity criteria (such as Glicksman's criteria), being geometrically miniaturized (e.g., at a 1:3 scale for hot facilities) (Habl *et al.*, 2017; Shrestha *et al.*, 2016). CFD can be used to analyze the scale-up and scale-down of these units, ensuring the maintenance of microstructure and design feasibility (Breault, 2024). Additionally, it allows for the evaluation of design and operational alternatives, although, without comprehensive experimental validation, the results may be more useful for qualitative analysis (Shah *et al.*, 2016).

CFD simulation contributes to overcoming experimental limitations. Measuring hydrodynamic parameters in industrial-scale plants under hot operating conditions is difficult and superficial (Shrestha *et al.*, 2016). Cold flow models, aided by CFD, offer an inexpensive and reliable source of fluid dynamics data, as they are easier to handle, require less equipment, and allow for visual observation of macroscopic flow structures (Shrestha *et al.*, 2016). Riser experiments rarely provide simultaneous observations on flow parameters and performance (conversion and yields) in real units, which has led to the development of CFD models (Shah *et al.*, 2016). CFD helps capture flow structures across various time and length scales that are challenging to observe experimentally (Shah *et al.*, 2016).

Despite advancements, CFD still faces challenges, such as the need for rigorous validation with comprehensive experimental data (Shah *et al.*, 2016). Future research in CFD for risers includes the use of methods like DEM for more realistic solid phase resolution, multiscale drag models for enhanced predictions, and LES simulations for turbulence parameters (Shah *et al.*, 2016). The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) with CFD is emerging as a way to overcome traditional computational and modeling limitations, offering greater efficiency, robustness, and scalability for complex flow simulations (Zhang *et al.*, 2025). simulation stands as an indispensable tool that, through the application of fundamental physical principles and robust numerical methodologies, facilitates a comprehensive understanding and optimized design of fluid and particle dynamics within cold riser pilot units, thereby surmounting the inherent practical and informational limitations of purely experimental investigations.

3 METHODOLOGY

A cold riser pilot unit from the Dr. Cornélius Keller Gamma Tomography Laboratory, Department of Nuclear Energy, Federal University of Pernambuco, was used to investigate the fluid dynamics of FCC systems and determine key operational parameters. The experimental setup includes a riser measuring 6.7 meters in height and 0.092 meters in internal diameter,

connected to a return column of similar dimensions through a separation vessel located at the top of the apparatus. The unit was specifically designed for two-phase (gas-solid) circulating flow and built with transparent acrylic to allow direct visual observation of internal flow structures. Three measurement sections were installed along the riser to monitor pressure and assess solids concentration using gamma-ray transmission techniques (DANTAS, C.C. *et al.*, 2013; SILVA *et al.*, 2021).

A detailed Three-Dimensional (3D) Computer-Aided Design (CAD) model of a cold FCC-type riser pilot unit had been previously developed in SolidWorks®, accurately replicating the physical geometry of the experimental setup. For the present study, only the fluid domain corresponding to the riser section was extracted and modeled for simulation purposes, rather than the entire pilot unit. Geometry editing and simplification were performed in ANSYS SpaceClaim to isolate the region of interest. Figure 1 presents a composite view of (a) the experimental unit, (b) the corresponding virtual 3D model, and (c) the fluid domain employed in the CFD simulations.

Figure 1

Composite representation of the cold riser pilot unit studied: (a) Experimental unit located at the Dr. Cornellius Keller Gamma Tomography Laboratory (UFPE); (b) Virtual 3D model of the complete pilot unit developed in SolidWorks®; (c) Computational fluid domain extracted from the riser region and used in the CFD simulations.

This study employed the ANSYS CFX software, version 2025 R1, to simulate and analyze the flow behavior of air and solid particles (Nylon-66) within a vertical riser. ANSYS CFX was selected due to its robustness in solving multiphase flows and its flexibility in defining fluid-particle interactions, making it a widely used tool in both industrial and scientific research on pneumatic conveying systems. The simulation methodology involved two stages. Initially, steady-state simulations were performed to assess the model's behavior and ensure the establishment of stable velocity, pressure, and particle distribution profiles along the riser. These preliminary runs allowed for a more efficient evaluation of boundary conditions and mesh quality. Subsequently, transient simulations were conducted to investigate the time-dependent dynamics of the gas-solid flow, capturing the evolution of flow structures, particle dispersion, and unsteady effects throughout the column. This combined approach enabled a comprehensive analysis while balancing computational cost and physical representativeness.

The computational mesh for the fluid domain was generated in ANSYS using a combination of automatic and custom methods to ensure accurate representation of critical flow regions. The MultiZone method, with prismatic decomposition for unidirectional flow areas, was used where applicable, while Patch Conforming with tetrahedral elements was employed for complex geometries such as mixers. For enhanced resolution near solid boundaries, particularly at the gas and solid inlets, the intersection between the inlet tube and the riser, and the riser outlet, the Inflation technique was applied using the "Pre" algorithm, with first-layer thicknesses between 3.5×10^{-4} m and 5.0×10^{-4} m, a growth rate of 1.2, and a maximum of five layers. Edge and face sizing combined absolute element sizes (1×10^{-3} m to 5×10^{-3} m) with division-based refinement (20 to 120 divisions per edge), ensuring local mesh refinement as needed. The mesh growth rate was kept at the default value of 1.2. Additional inflation settings included smooth transition and a transition ratio of 0.77.

Mesh quality was assessed using skewness and orthogonal quality as the primary metrics. The resulting mesh showed an average skewness of 0.14 (± 0.13) and an orthogonal quality above 0.85, confirming excellent numerical quality and stability. The final mesh comprised approximately 232,000 nodes and over 533,000 elements, representing a balanced trade-off between resolution and computational cost. To maintain control over mesh topology, adaptive automatic refinement was not used. Instead, manual defeaturing was applied to remove geometric details smaller than 1.67×10^{-3} m, enhancing robustness and solver performance. The quad-dominant and sweep methods were applied to sheet-like and sweepable bodies, respectively, and parallel partitioning was managed automatically. A final mesh quality check

indicated only minor skewness issues, with no significant impact on the accuracy or convergence of the simulations.

To model the flow behavior with adequate physical fidelity, the simulations solved the conservation equations for mass, momentum, turbulence kinetic energy, and eddy frequency. The Shear Stress Transport (SST) turbulence model was employed for its robust performance in near-wall regions and its ability to handle strong velocity gradients—characteristics typical of vertical gas-solid flows. The domain was defined as a stationary, isothermal region at 25 °C, a simplification justified by the negligible thermal gradients and absence of heat exchange in the system. Gravitational acceleration ($Y = -9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$) was applied to capture particle settling behavior, and buoyancy effects were included using a reference fluid density of 1.185 kg/m^3 , accounting for density differences between the gas and solid phases. Air was defined as the continuous phase, and Nylon-66 particles, modeled as "Particle Transport Solid" with a diameter of $80 \mu\text{m}$ and density of 1150 kg/m^3 , represented the dispersed phase due to their relevance in pneumatic transport applications and well-characterized properties.

Boundary conditions were defined to realistically represent the flow within the riser, based on experimental data from the cold pilot unit. At the gas inlet (Inlet 1), a static pressure of 14.565 kPa was applied. At the solid inlet (Inlet 2), a uniform injection of Nylon-66 particles was configured with a velocity of 0.46 m/s and a mass flow rate of 0.000077 kg/s, corresponding to approximately 250,000 particles per second. The use of uniform injection and a single particle position number served as a computationally efficient simplification for continuous particle loading. The outlet boundary was defined with a relative pressure of 246.69 Pa and flow normal to the surface, also based on experimental measurements. All internal walls were modeled as smooth and no-slip, with no erosion or surface roughness effects included, as the focus of the study was not on wall interactions or wear. Particle–wall and particle–particle interactions were modeled using the Sommerfeld collision framework, with restitution coefficients set to 0.90 and 0.95, respectively. These values reflect moderately elastic collisions, suitable for gas-solid flows involving Nylon-66 particles under dilute regime conditions, and account for realistic energy loss during impact without introducing excessive dissipation.

Phase interactions were analyzed through the implementation and comparison of two coupling strategies available in ANSYS CFX: one-way coupling and fully coupled interaction. These approaches were applied to steady-state simulations to evaluate their influence on flow predictions, particularly regarding momentum exchange between the fluid and the particle phases. The comparison results, detailed in the Results section, served as the basis for selecting

the most suitable strategy to be adopted in the subsequent transient simulations. The Schiller–Naumann drag force model was adopted, as it is widely accepted for flows involving small-diameter spherical particles under moderate Reynolds number conditions. The virtual mass force was included, with a coefficient of 0.5, to improve the accuracy of relative acceleration modeling between phases. Additionally, the turbulent dispersion force was activated using the “Particle Dispersion” option to account for the influence of turbulent eddies on particle motion. The pressure gradient force, in contrast, was excluded from the simulation due to its limited impact under the studied conditions. Although surface tension plays a limited role in gas-solid flows, it was defined as $46.175 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ to ensure consistency and completeness in the phase interaction model setup.

Solver control settings were configured to ensure numerical stability and accuracy in both steady-state and transient simulations. The High-Resolution advection scheme was employed to improve the accuracy of variable gradient capture, particularly in interphase regions. Turbulence discretization used a First-Order Upwind scheme to maintain solution stability throughout the domain. The timescale control was set to Auto Timescale, with the Conservative length scale option and a timescale factor of 1.0. For steady-state simulations, the solver was allowed a maximum of 1000 iterations, with a minimum of one iteration per cycle. For transient simulations, a total physical time of 100 seconds was simulated, using a fixed timestep of 0.001 s. Each timestep was allowed up to 100 iterations to ensure convergence, providing adequate temporal resolution to capture the unsteady evolution of flow structures and particle dynamics. In both cases, convergence was monitored using the RMS residual criterion, with a target threshold of 1×10^{-6} applied to all governing equations.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The first stage of the numerical study focused on evaluating the influence of phase coupling strategies on the predictive behavior of the CFD model. Two interaction models available in ANSYS CFX were tested under steady-state conditions: the one-way coupling, in which only the fluid phase influences the particles, and the fully coupled approach, where momentum exchange occurs bidirectionally between phases. This initial comparison aimed to identify the most appropriate strategy to be adopted in the subsequent transient simulations. To support this evaluation, several parameters were considered. The axial pressure distribution along the riser was analyzed based on experimental measurements obtained from pressure sensors installed at five distinct heights. Additionally, gas velocity profiles were extracted at

corresponding axial positions to evaluate the development of the flow and its interaction with the solid phase. Particle dispersion behavior was qualitatively assessed to verify the spatial uniformity of the solid phase within the column, identifying potential agglomeration or segregation phenomena. Beyond the physical fidelity of the results, computational performance was analyzed to support the selection of the most suitable phase coupling strategy. The evaluation considered the total simulation time, number of iterations required to reach convergence, RAM consumption, and the size of the generated output files. These metrics serve as practical indicators of computational cost and are especially relevant for future applications involving time-dependent simulations or larger and more complex domains, where efficiency becomes critical for feasibility.

The evaluation of the coupling strategies began with the analysis of pressure and velocity profiles, as presented in Table 1. The results revealed highly similar trends for both models along the riser, with negligible differences in predicted pressure values at all sensor locations. This consistency was especially evident in the mid and upper regions of the column, where variations remained below 1.5 Pa. Likewise, the predicted gas velocities were nearly identical, with maximum deviations not exceeding 0.06 m/s. These findings indicate that both coupling approaches capture the global flow behavior with comparable accuracy.

Table 1

Experimental and numerical results for pressure and velocity at different heights.

Height (m)	Sensor	Pressure			Velocity	
		Experimental (Pa)	One-Way (Pa)	Fully-Coupled (Pa)	One-Way (m/s)	Fully-Coupled (m/s)
0.24	PA	14589.07	14560.00	14560.00	38.67	38.67
0.79	PB	399.49	249.50	250.90	1.40	1.26
1.26	PD	—	249.30	250.60	1.65	1.65
2.13	P1	345.07	248.90	250.00	1.80	1.88
4.18	P2	301.92	247.90	248.60	1.87	1.92
6.03	P3	249.66	247.10	247.30	1.86	1.90
6.71	PF	—	246.80	246.80	1.86	1.90

Table 2 presents additional particle-level dispersion metrics, including average traveling distance and time, as well as maximum velocity components in the radial (u), axial (v), and tangential (w) directions. The fully coupled model yielded greater particle traveling distances and longer residence times, suggesting enhanced interaction between the phases and a more realistic representation of particle transport. Notably, the fully coupled model also showed slightly lower radial velocity peaks (u), which may indicate reduced artificial scattering of particles, while maintaining similar axial velocity and slightly increased tangential dispersion

(w). These patterns are consistent with more complex particle-fluid interactions and suggest a slightly improved fidelity in representing dispersion and potential segregation phenomena.

Finally, Table 3 compares the computational performance of the two coupling strategies. The fully coupled model required a substantially longer simulation time (5.33 hours vs. 0.72 hours) and a slightly higher number of iterations to convergence (904 vs. 871), both under the same RMS residual threshold. RAM consumption and output file size remained similar between approaches, suggesting that memory demand is not significantly impacted by the coupling method. However, the notable increase in processing time underscores the computational cost associated with bidirectional momentum exchange in the fully coupled strategy.

Table 2

Comparison of particle dispersion metrics based on traveling distance, time, and directional maximum velocity components (u , v , w) for one-way and fully coupled phase interaction models under steady-state conditions. Direction u corresponds to the radial (x) axis, v to the axial (y) axis, and w to the tangential (z) axis.

Phase strategies	coupling	Particle Traveling Distance (m)	Particle Time (s)	Traveling	Maximum (m/s)		
					u	v	w
One-Way		7.36	8.74		0.20	1.98	0.55
Fully-Coupled		9.40	9.64		0.12	1.98	0.76

Table 3

Computational performance comparison between the one-way and fully coupled phase interaction models under steady-state conditions.

Phase strategies	coupling	Simulation time (hours)	Number of iterations to convergence	RAM consumption (GB)	Output file size (GB)
One-Way		0.72	871	3.65	3.24
Fully-Coupled		5.33	904	3.71	3.21

Based on the combined analysis of flow accuracy, particle dispersion behavior, and computational performance, the one-way coupling strategy was selected for the transient simulations. Both coupling models produced nearly identical pressure and velocity profiles under steady-state conditions, and differences in particle transport metrics were minor. Although the fully coupled model offers marginally more detailed particle-fluid interaction, this advantage does not justify its significantly higher computational cost. A conservative extrapolation for the 100-second transient simulation indicates that the fully coupled approach would require over 24 days of computation, compared to approximately 3.5 days for the one-

way model. Considering the negligible gain in accuracy relative to the exponential increase in processing time, the one-way model provides a more practical and efficient solution for capturing the essential dynamics of the system in time-dependent scenarios.

Following the selection of the one-way coupling strategy, a time-dependent simulation was carried out to analyze the gas-solid flow behavior under unsteady conditions. This simulation aimed to capture the unsteady dynamics associated with particle injection, flow development, and the evolution of key hydrodynamic variables. The results presented below focus on the progression of velocity fields, pressure variations, and particle transport phenomena throughout the simulated period.

Figure 2 presents the streamlines of the gas velocity field at the final state of the transient simulation, colored by velocity magnitude. The flow is primarily driven by two inlets: Inlet 1, located at the bottom, introduces only gas from the compressor, while Inlet 2, positioned laterally, injects gas along with solid particles to represent the return flow characteristic of circulating fluidized bed systems.

Figure 2

Velocity streamline pattern at the transition from the Porous Zone to the Vertical Riser.

The highest velocities are observed at the base of the riser, just above Inlet 1, where the gas enters through a narrow vertical pipe and is rapidly accelerated through the porous distributor. This region forms a high-intensity upward jet that defines the core of the flow

structure. In contrast, the lateral Inlet 2 contributes a secondary gas stream accompanied by particles, which enters the riser with lower velocity magnitudes and follows more curved trajectories. Rather than producing a distinct recirculation zone, this stream gradually merges with the main upward flow, enhancing the overall mass flux and contributing to the entrainment and dispersion of the solid phase in the lower section of the riser.

Despite being partially penetrated by the gas flow, the porous distributor acts as a resistance zone that promotes velocity redistribution and reduces asymmetries near the wall. This configuration facilitates particle entrainment and promotes dispersion, especially near the riser core. When we compare our results with those of Silva (2017), we observe a similar flow pattern at the entry region: a jet is formed with the highest gas velocities concentrated near the connection between the solids feeder and the main riser body. However, Silva's model did not include a porous distributor, which limits a direct comparison regarding entrance effects and the behavior of the merging streams.

Figure 3 shows the solid particle velocity distribution along the riser at the final state of the transient simulation. Near the solids feed outlet, the solid particles reach high velocities, up to 2.2 m/s, a value significantly higher than the inlet conditions defined in the model (0.46 m/s for the solids and 1.76 m/s for the gas phase). This acceleration is driven by the interaction with the upward gas jet from Inlet 1. After approximately 3.5 m from the injection point, the particles decelerate and stabilize within an average velocity range between 0.7 and 1.7 m/s. These values are consistent with those reported in the previously mentioned literature. The stabilization of velocities beyond this region indicates the establishment of a drag-dominated regime, albeit still at a velocity range higher than initially expected.

In comparison with existing literature, Souza Netto *et al.* (2013), using a simplified riser geometry with a direct solid injection system, reported asymmetric flow patterns and average particle velocities around 1.7 m/s. Despite the differences in riser configuration, the velocity range obtained in their study (0.5–3.0 m/s) closely matches that observed in the present simulation. More recently, Silva *et al.* (2024), reported axial solid velocities between 0.5 and 2.0 m/s along the riser length, values that are also in line with those found in the current work. Although local velocities near the injection zone reached up to 3.0 m/s in our simulation, the average range remains compatible with experimental and numerical expectations. Occasional differences in maximum velocity may be attributed to variations in geometry, gas flow rate, or simulation time.

Figure 3

Solid particle velocity distribution along the riser.

Figure 4 displays the static pressure distribution along the riser at the final state of the transient simulation. The results show a typical behavior of upward gas-solid flows, with pressure values ranging from approximately 160 Pa to nearly 14,970 Pa. As expected, the most pronounced pressure gradient occurs near the gas inlet, just below the porous distributor. This region is characterized by rapid flow acceleration and significant momentum exchange, leading to a sharp drop in pressure.

Above the distributor, along the main vertical section of the riser, the pressure profile stabilizes and remains nearly constant, around 240–260 Pa. This behavior is consistent with a well-developed flow in which resistive forces have diminished, and the momentum of the continuous phase dominates the transport process. The enlarged view in Figure 4 highlights the intense pressure decay from the inlet to the distributor outlet, confirming the distributor's strong influence on system hydrodynamics.

These findings align well with previous studies. For instance, Souza Netto *et al.* (2013) reported a similar pressure drop across the distributor zone, with values falling from 107 kPa to 106.5 kPa along the riser. Although differences in units and boundary conditions prevent direct comparison, the qualitative trend of initial high pressure followed by stabilization remains

consistent. Likewise, Silva *et al.* (2020) observed a pressure decrease from 3164 Pa at the inlet of the porous zone to 259 Pa at the riser outlet, reinforcing the expected decay pattern in drag-dominated flows.

Figure 4

Static pressure distribution throughout the riser.

In summary, the results presented in this study provide an initial yet consistent representation of gas-solid two-phase flow within the modeled riser segment, serving as a proof of concept for the adopted modeling approach. The velocity and pressure fields, as well as particle dispersion behavior, followed expected trends and aligned well with previously reported experimental and numerical findings. Notably, the concentration of high velocities near the solids inlet and the formation of a coherent upward jet highlight the influence of geometric configuration on flow dynamics. The observed pressure stabilization along the vertical section and the particle velocity range (0.7–1.7 m/s) further confirm that the model reliably captured the dominant hydrodynamic regime.

Despite the robustness of the results, certain limitations must be acknowledged. The transient simulation was limited to 100 seconds and encompassed only a portion of the complete riser geometry, excluding the upper recirculation and separation zones. These simplifications may have restricted the full development of turbulence and long-term dispersion dynamics. Additionally, the isothermal assumption excluded thermal effects that could significantly

influence fluid properties and particle behavior in practical applications. When compared to other studies (Souza Netto *et al.*, 2013; Oliveira, 2018; Santos *et al.*, 2013; Silva, 2019; Vieira, 2022), which included longer simulation times (2000–2500 seconds) and modeled the entire riser, the current work focuses primarily on entrance region dynamics, limiting direct quantitative comparisons. Nevertheless, the outcomes remain physically coherent and provide a solid basis for future investigations incorporating extended domains, thermal modeling, or higher-fidelity turbulence approaches such as LES or DES.

5 CONCLUSION

This study presented the development and evaluation of an Euler–Lagrange CFD model to simulate gas-solid two-phase flow in a cold riser segment with an inclined inlet and a porous base zone. The numerical approach employed demonstrated physical consistency and produced results aligned with expected patterns for upward multiphase flow, including velocity distribution, pressure stabilization, and particle transport behavior.

Steady-state simulations comparing one-way and fully coupled interaction models revealed that both strategies yielded nearly identical pressure and velocity profiles. Although the fully coupled model presented slightly improved fidelity in capturing particle dispersion, its substantially higher computational cost led to the selection of the one-way approach for transient analysis. This decision was further supported by the minimal differences observed in key metrics and the practical need for computational efficiency.

The transient simulation results captured the flow structure and particle dynamics within the riser segment, particularly highlighting the formation of a high-velocity jet above the gas inlet and the gradual merging of the secondary stream containing solids. Velocity magnitudes and pressure profiles followed expected trends and matched reference values from the literature, even under the simplified isothermal and truncated domain conditions.

While limitations related to simulation time, geometric scope, and thermal effects were acknowledged, the findings remain physically robust. The model reliably reproduced critical hydrodynamic characteristics and offers a strong foundation for future studies, particularly those aiming to extend the simulation domain, incorporate energy transport, or explore higher-fidelity turbulence models.

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REFERENCES

- Breault, R. W. (2024). Scaling CFB risers: Beyond the data using microstructure similarity. *Powder Technology*, 433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2023.119237>
- Brito, M. F. P., Netto, W. F. S., Miranda, M. V. F. E. S., Junior, I. A. S., Dantas, C. C., Santos, V. A., Melo, S. B., & Lima, E. A. O. (2013). *MONITORING CATALYST FLOW RATE IN A FCC COLD PILOT UNITY BY GAMMA RAY TRANSMISSION MEASUREMENTS, 2013 International Nuclear Atlantic Conference - INAC 2013, 24-29.*
- Chang, J., Meng, F., Wang, L., Zhang, K., Chen, H., & Yang, Y. (2012). CFD investigation of hydrodynamics, heat transfer and cracking reaction in a heavy oil riser with bottom airlift loop mixer. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 78, 128–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2012.05.021>
- Chen, S., Fan, Y., Kang, H., Lu, B., Tian, Y., Xie, G., Wang, W., & Lu, C. (2021). Gas-solid-liquid reactive CFD simulation of an industrial RFCC riser with investigation of feed injection. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2021.116740>
- Crowe, C. T., Johnson, R., Prosperetti, A., Sommerfeld, M., & Tsuji, Y. (1996). Numerical methods for multiphase flows. *American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Fluids Engineering Division (Publication) FED*, 236(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2025.105285>
- Cui, M., Dikhtiarenko, A., Kulkarni, S. R., Shoinkhorova, T., Al Aslani, I., Alabdullah, M., Mazumder, J., Flores, R. M., Alahmadi, A., Alfilfil, L., Osorio, I. M., Almajnoui, K., Gascon, J., & Castaño, P. (2024). Regulating the crude oil-to-chemical process in a multizone fluidized bed reactor using unconventional catalyst formulations. *Powder Technology*, 438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2024.119573>
- Lima Filho, H. J. B., Brito, M. F. P. De, Benachour, M., Santos, V. A., & Dantas, C. C. (2015). *VALIDAÇÃO EXPERIMENTAL DE SIMULAÇÕES CFD DE UM LEITO FLUIDIZADO*

CIRCULANTE GÁS-SÓLIDO TIPO RISER, XX Congresso Brasileiro de Engenharia Química, 1, 2. <https://doi.org/10.5151/chemeng-cobeq2014-0255-26315-157415>

- Du, Y., Chen, X., Li, S., Berrouk, A. S., Ren, W., & Yang, C. (2022). Revisiting a large-scale FCC riser reactor with a particle-scale model. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2021.117300>
- Gómez-Velásquez, N., López-Montoya, T., Bustamante-Chaverra, C. A., & Nieto-Londoño, C. (2021). Parametric study of particles homogenization in cold-flow riser reactors. *International Journal of Thermofluids*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijft.2020.100058>
- Habl, M. A., Frohner, A., Tondl, G., & Pfeifer, C. (2017). Fluid dynamics study on a dual fluidized bed cold-flow model. *Powder Technology*, 316, 469–475. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2016.12.064>
- Hanchate, N., Malhotra, R., & Mathpati, C. S. (2021). Design of experiments and analysis of dual fluidized bed gasifier for syngas production: Cold flow studies. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 46(6), 4776–4787. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.02.114>
- Mirzaei, M., Clausen, S., Wu, H., Zakrzewski, S., Nakhaei, M., Zhou, H., Martin Jønck, K., Arendt Jensen, P., & Lin, W. (2023). CFD simulation and experimental validation of multiphase flow in industrial cyclone preheaters. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 465. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.142757>
- Nian, T., Li, D., Liang, Q., Wu, H., & Guo, X. (2021). Multi-phase flow simulation of landslide dam formation process based on extended coupled DEM-CFD method. *Computers and Geotechnics*, 140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2021.104438>
- Nigim, T. H. (2023). Novel classification of multistage flash desalination via finite and infinite flashing: Investigating thermofluid dynamics under varying inlet flow rates employing validated multiphase CFD simulations. In *Computers and Chemical Engineering* (Vol. 179). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2023.108437>
- Oliveira, M. F. M. de. (2018). *MODELAGEM DO TRANSPORTE DE SÓLIDOS EM REGIME DENSO EM UNIDADE PILOTO A FRIO POR MEDIÇÃO DE TRANSMISSÃO GAMA*, Master's Dissertation, Universidade Federal de Pernambuco.
- Porcu, R., Musser, J., Almgren, A. S., Bell, J. B., Fullmer, W. D., & Rangarajan, D. (2023). MFIX-Exa: CFD-DEM simulations of thermodynamics and chemical reactions in multiphase flows. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2023.118614>
- Reiss, C., Gerschenfeld, A., & Colin, C. (2024). Boiling-flow multiphase CFD simulations for nuclear reactor conditions without interfacial area transport equation. *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, 428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2024.113453>
- Riaz, S., Aaltonen, J., Pinkse, T., & Koskinen, K. (2025). Numerical investigation and validation of multiphase flow in annular jet pump—a mixture model approach. *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal*, 69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jestch.2025.102100>

- Santos, K. A. L. dos. (2013). *VALIDAÇÃO DA SIMULAÇÃO POR CFD DO RISER DE UMA UNIDADE PILOTO A FRIO DE FCC UTILIZANDO TRANSMISSÃO GAMA*, Master's Dissertation, Universidade Federal de Pernambuco.
- Shah, F., Fall, I., & Zhang, D. (2025). Breakage and coalescence mechanisms in multiphase flow comprehensive PBM-CFD review with turbulence modelling insights for gas-liquid system. In *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer* (Vol. 165). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icheatmasstransfer.2025.109093>
- Shah, M. T., Utikar, R. P., & Pareek, V. K. (2017). CFD study: Effect of pulsating flow on gas–solid hydrodynamics in FCC riser. *Particuology*, *31*, 25–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2016.07.002>
- Shah, M. T., Utikar, R. P., Pareek, V. K., Evans, G. M., & Joshi, J. B. (2016). Computational fluid dynamic modelling of FCC riser: A review. In *Chemical Engineering Research and Design* (Vol. 111, pp. 403–448). Institution of Chemical Engineers. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2016.04.017>
- Shrestha, S., Ali, B. S., & Binti Hamid, M. D. (2016). Cold flow model of dual fluidized bed: A review. In *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* (Vol. 53, pp. 1529–1548). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.09.034>
- Silva, A. C., Dantas, C. C., Melo, C. S., Viana, D. M. S., & Vieira, E. B. (2024). *3D CAD PILOT UNIT DESIGN AND SIMULATION OF TWO-PHASE FLOW CIRCULATION IN FULL LOOP WITH HIGH SOLIDS CONCENTRATION, 2024 International Nuclear Atlantic Conference – INAC 2024*.
- Silva, C. L., Bertony, V. E., C, D. C., Santos, B. E., & F M, O. M. (2018). Two-Phase Flow in 3D CAD Pilot Unit Simulation and Gamma Ray Tomography Validation. In *WORLD CONGRESS ON INDUSTRIAL PROCESS TOMOGRAPHY, 9th WORLD CONGRESS ON INDUSTRIAL PROCESS TOMOGRAPHY*.
- Silva, V. H. F. F. da. (2019). *INTEGRAÇÃO DE SIMULAÇÕES TOMOGRÁFICAS MCNPX ATRAVÉS DE IMPORTAÇÃO DA GEOMETRIA CFD DE FLUXO GÁS-SÓLIDO EM RISER A FRIO*. Maste's Dissertation, Universidade Federal de Pernambuco.
- Silva, L. C. (2017). *AVALIAÇÃO DA INTEGRIDADE ESTRUTURAL DE RISERS RÍGIDOS CONTENDO TRINCAS ATRAVÉS DA ABORDAGEM FAD COM BASE NA NORMA BS 7910 E SIMULAÇÕES COMPUTACIONAIS*. Maste's Dissertation, Universidade Federal de Pernambuco.
- Silva, V. H. F. F., Dantas, C. C., Melo, S. B., Lima, F. R. A., Oliveira, P. R. B., Resende Filho, T. A., Lins, J. A. G., Vieira, E. B., Andrade, B. G., & Viana, M. S. (2020). *Determination of fluid dynamic parameters through imports of CFD images validated in experiments for the MCNPX code, BRAZILIAN JOURNAL OF RADIATION SCIENCES*.
- Souza Netto, W. F. de, Brito, M. F. P., Dantas, C. C., Silva, J. M. F. da, Santos, V. A., Freitas, R. B., & Barbosa, E. S. (2013). *A FLUID DYNAMIC MODEL FOR CATALYST FLOW IN RISER OF A FCC COLD PILOT UNITY IS VALIDATED BY GAMMA RAY TRANSMISSION MEASUREMENTS. 2013 International Nuclear Atlantic Conference - INAC 2013, 24-29*.

- Sun, S., Bo, K., Jia, R., Cao, P., Chen, B., & Guo, M. (2023). Experimental investigation and CFD simulation of multiphase flow behavior in air reverse circulation drilling. *Advanced Powder Technology*, 34(10). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appt.2023.104168>
- Tang, J., Cheng, Z., Zhang, X., Sun, J., Liu, Z., Zhang, H., Tan, S., & Qiu, F. (2024). Continuous ultrasonic ozone coupling technology-assisted control of ceramic membrane fouling coupled enhanced multiphase mixing to treat dye wastewater and CFD flow field simulation. *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry*, 104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultsonch.2024.106839>
- Tripoonsuk, C., Chalermisinsuwan, B., & Piumsomboon, P. (2025). Computational fluid dynamics in ICFB reactor: Effect of proportion of riser and downer on system hydrodynamics. *Results in Engineering*, 25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.104187>
- Vieira, E. B. (2022). *PROJETO E CONSTRUÇÃO DE PLANTA VIRTUAL EM AMBIENTE 3D DA UNIDADE PILOTO A FRIO TIPO FCC PARA COMPARAÇÃO E VALIDAÇÃO DE PARÂMETROS FLUIDODINÂMICOS COM TOMOGRAFIA GAMA*. Master's Dissertation. Universidade Federal de Pernambuco.
- Villafañe, L., Aliseda, A., Ceccio, S., Di Marco, P., Machicoane, N., & Heindel, T. J. (2025). 50 Years of International Journal of Multiphase Flow: Experimental methods for dispersed multiphase flows. *International Journal of Multiphase Flow*, 189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2025.105239>
- Wang, J., Xu, J., Liu, H., & Gong, J. (2024). Simulation analysis of gas-solid two-phase flow and reaction in a novel catalytic cracking reactor. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis*, 183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2024.106792>
- Yan, Z., Wang, D., Wu, L., & Lu, C. (2024). Mixing effects of high-speed jets in gas-solid riser and downer reactors. *Particuology*, 92, 196–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2024.05.010>